

Synthesis of strapped nickel(II) macrocyclic complex of tetraaza[14]annulene

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A description has been made of the reaction of 7,12-dimethyl-5,14 diphenyldibenzo[*b,i*][1,4,8,11]tetraazacyclododecatrienone nickel(II) further denoted tetraaza[14]annulene nickel(II) with 3,3'-(2,6-pyridinedioxy)dibenzoyl chloride hydrochloride which afforded the corresponding strapped Ni^{II} complex containing an interactive pyridine group. The infrared spectrum showed the presence of the C=O stretching band at 1670 cm⁻¹ and of the C–O–C stretching bands at 1054 and 1228 cm⁻¹. The structure of the strapped macrocyclic complex is confirmed by elemental and spectral analysis.

Recent years have witnessed a growing interest toward macrocyclic complexes of transition and post-transition metals mainly because of their involvement as diagnostic agents in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)¹. In dealing with these applications, Gd^{III} is the ion of choice for its high effective magnetic moment and for the long electronic relaxation time associated with the *f*⁷-configuration. A good ability to enhance the water proton nuclear magnetic relaxation rates represents obviously a basic prerequisite for any paramagnetic complex to be considered as a potential contrast agent (CA) in MRI^{1,2}.

A route to remarkably improve the relaxation enhancement capability of Gd^{III} complexes lies in the possibility of lengthening their molecular reorientational time. This target may be pursued through the formation of macromolecular complexes. Furthermore, the introduction of the pyridine in the macrocyclic ring is expected to increase the stereochemical rigidity of the resulting complexes, a property often associated with an increase in their thermodynamic stability. The pyridine moiety may also provide a suitable site for a successive functionalization which facilitates the process of molecular recognition towards target. Keeping these points in view, it has been planned to synthesize macrocyclic complexes possessing a pyridine moiety out of the macrocyclic ring which is considered a novel strapped tetraaza[14]annulene nickel(II) complex.

Results and Discussion

The strapped tetraaza[14]annulene-Ni^{II} complex (H) (Scheme 1) was synthesized according to literature method³. A synthetic route shows the synthesis of tetraaza[14]annulene-Ni^{II} with 3,3'-(2,6-pyridinedioxy)dibenzoyl chloride (F) according to reported method³. The in-

frared spectrum of F showed strong absorption bands at 1772 and 1745 cm⁻¹ due to carbonyl stretching mode. The splitting is due to fermi resonance⁴. The mass spectrum of F exhibited the expected molecular ion peak at *m/z* 415. As the ring closure takes place, the possibility of forming a dimer and an oligomer increases. The new strapped tetraaza[14]annulene nickel(II) complex (H) was synthesized by refluxing G and F. IR spectrum of H was similar to that of

Scheme 1

unbridged complex (G) which showed strong C=O bands at 1658 (C=O), ~1220 and 1052 cm^{-1} (C-O-C). The electronic spectra of G and H were similar in the range 15000–4000 cm^{-1} . Macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} showed no significant bands at ~17000 cm^{-1} . This type of spectral behavior is similar to the square-planar complex of Ni^{II} . The molar extinction coefficients of the bands above 17080 cm^{-1} were found slightly larger in magnitude than those assigned for $d \rightarrow d^*$ transitions. These bands are presumed to be charge transfer and/or $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions⁵. This is due to that all $d \rightarrow d^*$ bands were obscured by the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and charge transfer bands whose intensity is high. It is opined that strapped complex of Ni^{II} (H) has square-planar configuration. Magnetic measurement values show that the complex H is diamagnetic. In MNR (Table 1) the methine proton signal of H disappeared due to bridging reaction and new signal appeared at δ 5.34 (s) due to methylene protons of the bridging group and at δ 7.34–8.52 (m) due to aromatic and pyridinic proton signals. As it is well known that aromatic proton signals in the macrocyclic group do not shift to upfield, the pyridine in the bridging group does not participate in the axial bond formation with nickel⁶. It may be considered due to the fact that bridging linkage is not flexible as compared to that of a polymethylene chain and as there is no solvent peak indication for this strapped system.

Table 1. Proton NMR spectral data (δ) of macrocyclic complex of Ni^{II} (H)^a

Compd.	-CH ₃	-CH-	-OCH ₂ -	Aromatic	
				Macrocyclic	Strapped
G ^a	2.09 (s)	4.86 (s)		6.44–6.80 (m)	
H ^b	1.90 (s)		5.34 (s)	6.60 (s br)	7.34–8.52 (m)
H ^{1c}	1.85 (s)		5.35 (s)	6.59–6.87 (m)	7.50–8.34 (m)

^aRef. 8. ^bIn CDCl_3 (present work). ^cIn $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ (present work).

Experimental

Macrocyclic complexes : Dimethylpyridine-2,6-dicarboxylate (B), 2,6-bis(hydroxymethyl)pyridine (C), 2,6-bis(bromomethyl)pyridine (D), 3,3'-(2,6-pyridinedioxy)dibenzoic acid (E), 3,3'-(2,6-pyridinedioxy)dibenzoyl chloride hydrochloride (F) and 7,12-dimethyl-5,14-diphenyldibenzo[*b,i*][1,4,8,11]tetraazacyclotetradecinatoni-

ckel(II) (G) were prepared according to the field methods reported in the literature^{3–6}. The macrocyclic complex of nickel(II) (H) was prepared by refluxing a mixture of F (0.048 g) and G (0.346 g) dissolved in benzene/ CH_2Cl_2 (1 : 1; 400 ml) containing triethylamine (1.2 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 8 days and then filtered to remove triethylamine hydrochloride. The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator. The solid obtained was subjected to TLC on silica gel using CHCl_3 as a developing solvent to give fine green crystals (~80%), m.p. >400°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1660 (C=O), 1225 and 1055 cm^{-1} (C-O-C). C, H, N analyses were found satisfactory.

Proton NMR spectra ($\text{CDCl}_3/\text{DMSO}-d_6$) were recorded on a FT NMR A.C. 300 spectrophotometer relative to TMS as an internal reference standard, IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1800 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (CHCl_3) on a Shimadzu DU7 spectro-photometer and mass spectra on a VG 70-S GCMS instrument.

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